

Beyond the catalyst: Role of the cell configuration, electrolyte concentration and ionomer content on the performance of Cu based CO₂ electrolyzers.

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Abstract

The performance of CO₂ electrolyzers is dictated by both the catalyst used and the interfacial reaction microenvironment. In this study we systematically explore the effect of two parameters affecting the microenvironment – electrolyte concentration and ionomer content across the three commonly used electrolyser configurations (H-cell, catholyte-flow GDE, and zero-gap GDE) – on the performance of Cu-based electrodes. These parameters were investigated in isolation and for different combinations of electrolyte concentration and ionomer content. The performance trends of these Cu-based electrodes showed a strong correlation with variations in the electrolyte concentration, the ionomer content, and the cell configuration. The selectivity of the zero-gap electrolyzers was found to be affected by changes in the electrolyte concentration while catholyte-flow and H-cell configurations were largely insensitive to electrolyte concentration across the tested range. Additionally, it was seen that increasing amounts of Nafion in the catalyst layer shifted the selectivity from C₂₊ products to CO for both the zero-gap and catholyte-flow GDEs. This effect of Nafion content was found to be more substantial for the case of the catholyte flow electrolyzers. Zero-gap electrolyzers were seen to be affected by both the electrolyte concentration and ionomer content whereas the catholyte-flow GDEs only showed a strong dependency on the ionomer content. Conversely, the selectivity of H-cells remained invariant to both the electrolyte and ionomer content. Catholyte-flow GDEs with Nafion in the catalyst layers showed ~80% FEs towards CO on Cu based GDEs at current densities >100 mA/cm². We postulate in this study that the differences across cell configurations could arise due to the differing amounts of cations in the catalytic microenvironment which are known to positively affect the C₂/C₁ product ratios. Both the electrolyte concentration and ionomer content are known to affect the local cation concentration and therefore the electrolyser selectivity. Operando X-ray absorption spectroscopy, glovebox-

assisted X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) were used to study the microenvironment dependent speciation differences and SEM-EDS on FIB milled samples was used to evaluate potassium concentration gradients in the cross-section of the gas diffusion layer.

1. Introduction

As the field of electrochemical carbon dioxide conversion matures and moves up the technology readiness level (TRL) ladder, the focus of research shifts from catalyst discovery to solving industrial implementation challenges. Initial catalyst-based research looked at the classification of elements and their selectivity towards different CO₂ reduction (CO₂R) products.¹⁻⁴ Recent advances in computational and synthetic capabilities have led to the exploration of the bimetallic/multi-metallic catalyst space to break scaling relations and obtain performances (activity and selectivity) better than monometallic catalysts and to reduce dependence on critical rare-earth metal catalysts.⁵⁻⁹ While initial studies provided pertinent information about catalyst dependent selectivity behaviour, recent focus has shifted towards understanding the catalytic microenvironment and its impact on the electrolyser performance.¹⁰⁻¹³ It is essential to understand the impact of the catalytic microenvironment as the performance of the catalyst, its repeatability across research groups and electrolyser stability is highly dependent on the interfacial microenvironment.

The effect of cations and their concentration on the activity and selectivity of CO₂ electrolysis has been a topic of research in the last few years.¹⁴⁻¹⁷ Incorporation of ionomers, binders and other additives to improve the hydrophobicity, adhesion, and stability of the catalyst nanoparticles has also been investigated.¹⁸⁻²¹ Historically, the activity of the catalysts was evaluated in H-cell like device architecture while industrial applicability requires transitioning to gas diffusion electrode (GDE) based electrolyzers that facilitate higher production rates.²²⁻²⁴ It is observed that for

different electrolyzers configurations the activity/selectivity trends do not directly translate for the same catalysts due to differing interfacial microenvironments.^{25–28} Therefore, it is essential that the microenvironment and its impact on electrolyser performance is investigated separately across different cell configurations.

Different cell architectures, due to their fundamental design differences can lead to differing concentrations of cations and free water in the catalyst layer both of which can have a profound impact on the electrolyser performance. The cation concentration and water content in the catalyst layer can be affected by changing the electrolyte concentration, incorporating hydrophobic ionomers, and the choice of cell configuration. In this work, we aim to reconcile these two factors affecting the catalytic microenvironment across the three different cell configurations and study these factors both in isolation and concurrently. We systematically investigate the impact of ionomer content, and electrolyte concentration on the performance of Cu-based electrodes across three different cell configurations (H-cell, catholyte-flow GDE, and zero-gap GDE). Commercial copper nano-powders (40-60 nm, Sigma Aldrich) spray deposited onto Freudenberg H23C6 gas diffusion layers were used as the cathode across all measurements. An anion exchange membrane (PiperION) was used to separate the anodic and cathodic half cells. Electrolyte concentrations from 0.02 M to 1.5 M were used to study the electrolyte concentration dependent selectivity trends. The loading of the ionomer (Nafion) in the catalyst ink dispersion was also systematically varied, and its impact investigated for the three different cells. We employed glovebox-assisted X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy, and *operando* X-ray absorption spectroscopy to investigate surface speciation related selectivity differences. Scanning electron microscopy -and elemental mapping was performed on the cross-section of samples to map potassium concentrations as a function of thickness across the cell types.

2. Methods and Materials (More information in SI)

Three electrolyser configurations were chosen for the purposes of this study. They are summarized below and schematically depicted in Figure 1 –

- a) H-cell: This cell architecture allows for rapid screening and control over the working electrode potentials but suffers from low reaction rates due to mass transport limitations arising from limited aqueous solubility of CO₂. The home-made H-cell consisted of two glass compartments separated by a membrane (AEM). The cathodic half of the cell consisted of the working electrode, Cu spray deposited onto gas diffusion layers (more information in the methods section), and an Ag/AgCl reference electrode. CO₂ was bubbled into the electrolyte through a porous frit at the bottom of the cell at a constant flow rate of 20 ml/min. A platinum wire was used as the counter electrode in the anodic compartment of the cell. The electrolyte volume was 30 ml in both compartments. The working electrode area for the H-cell experiments was adjusted between 0.3cm² to 1cm² and the currents were normalized with respect to the geometric area. For large overpotentials (large currents), smaller working electrode areas were used to overcome potentiostat compliance issues and for lower overpotentials (lower currents) larger working electrode areas were used to facilitate accurate product analysis using gas chromatography.
- b) Catholyte-flow GDE: To overcome mass transport related limitations associated with H-cells, the reactant CO₂ is fed in gaseous form to the electrode in this reactor configuration. This cell consisted of two chambers separated by an anion exchange membrane for the cathodic and anodic half reactions. The electrode active area was set to 0.5 cm² by rubber gaskets. The counter electrode was a 1.5 cm² iridium coated gas diffusion layer (GDL). Humidified CO₂ was purged from behind the catalyst through a serpentine flow pattern at a

constant flow rate of 30 ml/min. Separate electrolytes for the cathode (catholyte) and anode (anolyte), each of 25 ml volume and held in external reservoirs, were circulated through the respective chambers at 21 ml/min. The current collectors for both the working and counter electrodes were made of gold coated stainless steel.

- c) Zero-gap GDE: The zero-gap GDE cell configuration (eChemicles Zrt., CO₂ electrolyzer test cell) was based on the designs reported in the publications of Endrődi et al²⁹⁻³¹ and has been discussed in detail in our previous work.¹⁵ The Cu coated gas diffusion layer (active area 8 cm²) was placed on top of a stainless steel cathodic current collector and was held in place by a 200 μm thick PTFE spacer which resulted in a GDL compression of ~20% in relation to its original thickness. The anode compartment consisted of Ir-coated Ti frits with the Ir coated side facing the Cu coated cathode. The two compartments were separated by an anion-exchange membrane, against which the electrodes were physically pressed during cell assembly. Humidified CO₂ was fed to the cathode at a constant flow rate of 60 ml/min using a Bronkhorst El-Flow prestige mass flow controller. Feed gas humidification was achieved by flowing the gas through 15 ml ultra-pure water in a gastight 100 ml DURAN bottle. The anode side consisted of an electrolyte solution flowing through the porous frit anode, circulated by peristaltic pump from a reservoir of 25 ml at a flow rate of 21 ml/min.

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the three different cell configurations - a) H-cell, b) catholyte-flow GDE, c) Zero-gap GDE. WE, CE and AEM refer to working electrode, counter electrode and anion exchange membrane respectively.

Electrochemical characterization

The electrochemical measurements were carried out using a Biologic SP-300 potentiostat equipped with a 4 A current booster. The zero-gap experiments were conducted in a two-electrode configuration with the cell voltage being the voltage difference between the anode and the cathode. The catholyte and H-cell experiments were conducted in the three-electrode configuration with a Ag/AgCl reference electrode. For the three electrode measurements (catholyte-flow GDE and H-cell) an automatic software based 85% iR compensation was used, where the iR drop was determined via electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) at the open circuit potential. EIS spectra were collected at open circuit and at onset, before and after the chronopotentiometry (CP) / chronoamperometry (CA). All electrochemical measurements and components were operated at ambient temperature without additional thermal control or stirring.

Product Analysis

Gaseous products were analyzed using in-line gas chromatography (SRI MG 5) every 18.33 minutes. A typical injection required 13.33 minutes while 5 additional minutes between injections were required for device equilibration. The GC is equipped with two detectors, a thermal conductivity detector (TCD) for the detection of H₂, O₂, and N₂, and a flame ionization detector (FID) with a methanizer for the detection of CO, CH₄, C₂H₄, C₂H₆. A 5-point calibration was performed for all gases. The hydrocarbons, hydrogen and CO were calibrated between 100 to 10000 ppm whereas Nitrogen was calibrated up to 25%. The gas chromatograph offers two sensitivity modes, the high sensitivity mode was used for the H-cell experiments due to low production rates whereas the low sensitivity mode was used for the zero-gap GDE and catholyte-flow GDE experiments. The liquid products were analyzed by high-performance liquid chromatography (Thermo Scientific UltiMate 3000 series) which was equipped with UV variable wavelength (UltiMate 3000, Dionex) and refractive index (RefractoMax 520, ERC) detectors. A HyperRez XP H+ column with a mobile phase of 5mM H₂SO₄ was used. Liquid samples for the zero gap electrolyzers were collected from the anolyte solution and a water trap in the cathode side at the end of each experiment. For the catholyte-flow GDE and H-cell experiments, both catholyte and anolyte liquid samples were collected and analyzed.

Materials

All chemicals used in this study were purchased from VWR International, Merck, or Fuel Cell Store. The chemicals were used without any further purification. The copper nanopowders (40-60nm), Nafion perfluorinated resin (5 wt. % in mixture of lower aliphatic alcohols and water, contains 45% water) and potassium hydroxide (ACS reagent, ≥85%, pellets) were purchased from Merck. Iridium HSA and the PiperION AEM (20um) were purchased from Fuel Cell Store.

Ultrapure water (~18 M Ω) was used for these experiments for electrolyte preparation and as the water trap. A 4.8 purity CO₂ cylinder from Linde was used as the CO₂ source.

Electrode fabrication

- *Cathode*: The cathode GDEs were prepared by spray coating an ink solution onto Freudenberg H23C6 GDLs using a hand-held airbrush. The ink consisted of the copper nanopowders (40-60nm, Merck), varying wt% of Nafion in a 1:1 IPA:water mixture. This dispersion was spray-coated onto the GDL resting on a hot plate set to 185°C. The catalyst loading was fixed to 1mg/cm² for all measurements.
- *Anode*: The anodes were prepared by spray coating a dispersion containing, 1:1 isopropanol: water, Iridium HSA (Fuel Cell Store) and 15 wt.% Sustainion ionomer onto 8.0 cm² porous Ti frits. (Changsheng Titanium Co., Ltd, 1.0 mm thickness and 225 microns average grain size) The loading of the anode was also fixed at 1mg/cm². Prior to coating, the catalyst inks of both the anode and cathode were homogenized in an ultrasonic bath for 30 minutes.

Characterization

- A focused ion beam (FIB) system (Zeiss Crossbeam 340 KMAT dual beam) was used to prepare cross sections at the catalyst-GDE interface of electrodes after testing, which were then imaged using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with elemental mapping via energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). For milling the samples and preparing the cross-sections, the FIB-SEM EDS system was equipped with a Ga ion source. The milling cut was performed using an acceleration voltage of 30 kV and two different polishing currents (80 nA for rough cut and 1.5 nA for fine polishing).

- X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS): XPS measurements were carried out using an Al K α X-ray source (1486.74 eV) and hemispherical XPS analyzer (SPECS Phoibos 100) equipped with a SPECS FOCUS 500 monochromator. The pass energy was set to 10eV with a step size of 0.05eV. All spectra were calibrated with respect to the C 1s peak at 284.5 eV. The spectra were fitted in CasaXPS software using a Shirley background subtraction. Before XPS analysis, samples from electrolysis experiments were extracted and transferred without air exposure to the XPS system, to avoid O₂-induced surface oxidation.
- X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) was conducted at the KMC-2 beamline of the BESSY II synchrotron³² using an adapted cell described in our previous work¹⁵ The Cu K-edge XANES (X-ray absorption near-edge spectroscopy) and EXAFS (extended X-ray absorption fine structure) were measured using a fluorescence detector (Si-PIN photodiode), during operation of the electrochemical cells under CO₂ reduction conditions. XANES and EXAFS spectra were collected between 8826 eV and 9623 eV (k=13). At least 2 repetitions were collected for each condition and averaged where each measurement run required ~30 minutes. FT-EXAFS analysis was conducted by k²-weighted fourier transform in the k range 3-11. Reference spectra for metallic Cu, CuO, Cu(OH)₂, and Cu₂O were collected in fluorescence and transmission modes. All the spectra were processed in Athena software from the Demeter 0.9.26 software suite using metallic Cu spectrum as a reference for energy calibration.³³

3. Results

Electrolyte concentration dependent selectivity trends across cell configurations.

In our previous work, we highlighted the consequences of unintended cation crossover from the anode to the cathode (through an anion exchange membrane) in Cu-based zero-gap electrolyzers¹⁵. We found that the electrolyte concentration in the anolyte directly affected the magnitude of cation crossover, which correlated prominently with altered CO₂ reduction product selectivity trends. This observation led us to wonder why, despite years of research on Cu-based CO₂ reduction, this trend in electrolyte-dependent selectivity tuning had seldom been observed. We hypothesize that the phenomenon is particularly sensitive to the cell configuration, and hence the resulting microenvironment. Here, we investigate this question by conducting studies of replicate Cu-based electrodes across three distinct cell configurations. To affect the local cation concentration around the catalyst we examined two approaches – i) varying the electrolyte concentration and ii) incorporating an ionomer (Nafion) and systematically varying the ionomer content in the catalyst ink dispersion.

Figure 2. Electrolyte concentration dependent CO₂R selectivity trends for zero-gap (a,c) and catholyte configuration (b,d) as a function of Nafion concentration. Catalysts with no Nafion (a,b) and with 13% Nafion (c,d). All the experiments were carried out at a constant current of 100 mA/cm². Data for each electrolyte concentration is obtained using replicate Cu-GDEs, and each point represents the average of 3 sequential GC injections. Lines are drawn between points to guide the eye, and the x-axes values are not positioned to scale. Only major gaseous products are shown.

Comparisons of CO₂R selectivity between the zero-gap and catholyte flow cell using varied KOH electrolyte concentrations are shown in Figure 2. The zero-gap electrolyser (Figure 2a) exhibits a clear selectivity trend with concentration, while no such trend is observed for the catholyte flow cell configuration (Figure 2b). For the zero-gap electrolyser, on decreasing the electrolyte concentration from 1M to pure water, the selectivity towards C₂H₄ gradually decreases,

accompanied by a concurrent increase in H₂ and CO selectivity. A peak CO FE% of ~50% was observed at 0.02 M KOH whereas the peak FE% towards C₂H₄ of ~35% was observed for 1.0 M KOH. Across a range of electrolyte conditions, the catholyte-flow configuration showed little variance in selectivity, with only H₂ showing a slight trend. It should be noted that concentrations below 0.1 M were not accessible for the catholyte configuration due to potentiostat voltage compliance issues due to the low conductivity. But the differences between the two cell configurations are stark at these intermediate concentrations of 0.1-0.3 M.

Next, wanted to evaluate whether incorporating Nafion in the catalyst layer led to differences in the selectivity trends across the two cell configurations (Fig. 2c and 2d). Prior reports have shown that Nafion incorporation leads to a change in the selectivity distribution, and we intended to assess whether these trends were consistent across cell configurations for replicate Cu GDEs.^{18,20} While a concentration dependent selectivity trend was still observed for the zero-gap case, the concentration for the peak CO FE% shifted up from 0.02 M to 0.1 M. The ethylene efficiencies showed a similar behavior to the case of 0% Nafion as the FE% increased with increasing electrolyte concentrations peaking at 1M KOH. For the catholyte-flow configuration, a stark difference in selectivity emerged with Nafion incorporation, (Figure 2d), resulting in CO becoming the dominant product (70-80% FE) across all concentrations tested. This increase in CO came at the expense of H₂ and C₂H₄ which both dropped to >15%. While the incorporation of Nafion shifted the selectivity drastically in the case of the catholyte-flow case, the insensitivity to varied electrolyte concentration still held.

The aforementioned gas-fed GDE studies were performed using constant current density as the basis for comparison, because both cells were capable of such current densities (100 mA/cm²) and the absence of a reference electrode in the zero-gap cell precluded testing under precise potential-

controlled conditions. Conversely, in the H-cell configuration (electrode immersed in CO₂-saturated electrolyte) such currents cannot be achieved, but a reference electrode is present. Hence, further experiments using fixed electrode potential (-1.6 V vs Ag/AgCl) were conducted to compare the catholyte-flow and H-cell configurations. Again, we compared the CO₂R selectivity as a function of electrolyte concentration and Nafion incorporation between replicate electrodes in the two types of cells. (Figure 3).

Figure 3. CO₂ reduction selectivity trends across the catholyte-flow (a,c) and H-cell configuration (b,d) as a function of KOH anolyte concentration (x-axis not to scale). Cu-GDE cathodes are prepared without Nafion (a,b) and with 9%

Nafion (c,d). All the experiments were carried out at -1.6 V vs Ag/AgCl. The chronoamperometry data for these experiments is provided in SI Fig. S1 and S2

Comparing the catholyte-flow and the H-cell configurations it is seen that for the case without any Nafion, Figure 3a and Figure 3b, both configurations show similar electrolyte concentration dependent selectivity trends for ethylene, CO and hydrogen. While there are no pronounced trends for these two products in both the cell configurations, a gradual increase in the C₂H₄ FEs is observed on increasing electrolyte concentration from 0.1 M to 0.8 M in Figure 3c. The selectivity towards CO is also found to decrease with increasing electrolyte concentrations beyond 1 M in the catholyte case. Our hypothesis for these lies in the differing partial current densities for the catholyte-flow cell while the mass transport of species remains the same. The chronoamperometry data for the different electrolyte concentrations with and without Nafion incorporation is plotted in Figure S2. On incorporating Nafion in the catalyst layer for the catholyte-flow case, it is once again observed that the selectivity towards CO drastically increases (~90% FE), consistent with the data shown in Figure 2. Concurrently, the selectivity towards hydrogen is suppressed from 30%-40% to under 10% upon Nafion incorporation. The H-cell configuration on the other hand shows no obvious electrolyte concentration dependent selectivity trends for both the case with Nafion (Figure 3b) and without (Figure 3d).

To summarize the observations seen across the three cells, the zero-gap cell is affected both by the electrolyte concentration and the incorporation of Nafion, the catholyte-flow cell is mainly affected by the Nafion incorporation, and the H-cell appears mostly unaffected by either. The electrolyte concentration dependent selectivity trends are more pronounced in zero-gap cells whose use has only recently gained traction in the research field. As such these trends are under-reported due to zerogap cells being less studied, but we have observed similar trends in our previous work.¹⁵

Nafion concentration dependent selectivity trends across cell configurations

To further understand the impact of Nafion incorporation on the selectivity trends for the catholyte-flow and the zero-gap configurations, a series of controlled current experiments (between 100-300 mA/cm²) with varying Nafion amounts were carried out (Figure 4). H-cell tests were omitted since it was found that Nafion had little effect on that configuration (Figure 3b,d). Experiments were carried out using two different electrolyte concentrations, 1 M KOH and 0.5 M KOH for both the GDE electrolyser configurations. Three general observations that can be drawn from the dataset are –

- Increase in the CO selectivity at the expense of hydrogen and ethylene on increasing Nafion concentrations for both the cell configurations. While peak C₂H₄ FEs are observed at low Nafion concentrations, peak CO FEs are observed at higher Nafion concentrations.
- At higher current densities (300 mA/cm²), the catholyte-flow cell configuration shows lower H₂ FEs in comparison to the zero-gap GDE configuration where the H₂ selectivity increases on increasing current densities. This indicates that the catholyte-flow GDE configuration with the flowing catholyte is more stable in our measurement conditions and devoid of flooding at elevated current densities.
- A significant amount of acetate is formed for samples with little to no Nafion incorporation and seemed to be suppressed at higher Nafion contents. For the lower Nafion concentrations in the catholyte cell configuration, the FEs do not add up to 100% due to a loss of liquid products either in the catalyst layer, or in the gas out tube. Liquid samples

were only collected from the catholyte and the anolyte reservoirs and not the gas out tube which was directly fed to the GC.

Figure 4. Impact of Nafion incorporation on the selectivity of zero-gap GDE (a) (c) and catholyte-flow GDE (b) (d) at current densities between 100-300 mA/cm² under two different KOH concentrations – 1M (a) (b) and 0.5M (c) (d). The same electrode was used for measuring the cluster of three current densities, the FE values are an average of 3 injections.

Microenvironment effects revealed by cation distribution

As summary of the previous sections, factors which influence the catalytic microenvironment (cell configuration, electrolyte concentration, ionomer incorporation) each clearly play important roles in determining product selectivity, and importantly, our observations from testing various combinations of these parameters reveal strong interplay between them. While the influence on

macroscopic phenomena like hydrophobicity and mass transport certainly contribute (e.g. in the suppression of H₂ evolution), we hypothesize that differences in the microscale behavior of electrolyte ions may be a key factor influencing the product selectivity trends.

Cation effects and the mechanisms by which they affect activity and selectivity have been widely discussed in literature. Alkali metal cations are known to promote electrochemical CO₂ conversion reaction and influence selectivity: studies have shown that increasing the cation concentration decreases the overpotential for the onset of CO₂R.^{14,17,34-36} On Cu, an inverse relationship between the cation concentration and the selectivity of CO₂R towards CO has also been observed.^{15,36} We suspect that the selectivity trends on Cu GDEs observed herein also arise because of potentially different local cation concentrations which are in turn affected by the cell configuration, electrolyte and Nafion concentration. While cation concentration dependent selectivity trends have already been reported by both experimental and theoretical studies in literature, the differences across cell configurations and the rationale behind them have been less examined.

For experiments with varying electrolyte concentration (Figure 2), strong trends in product selectivity are observed for the zero-gap configuration which are not evident for the catholyte-flow cell. We hypothesize that this difference between the two cell types arises due to the cell geometry, the central difference being the absence or presence of a liquid catholyte, leading to altered supply of electrolyte ions to the catalytic interface. The zero-gap GDE cells when first assembled have no discrete catholyte contacting the cathode, but eventually electrolyte cations from the anolyte do reach the cathode, influenced by migration, diffusion, and the ion-selective properties (i.e. Donnan potential) of the AEM-anolyte interface.^{24,37} Variation of electrolyte concentration modulates these forces, and our previous study showed that anolyte concentration correlates directly with the amount of cations reaching the cathode which in turn correlates with distinct trends in CO₂

reduction selectivity.¹⁵ We found increasing cation concentrations led to enhanced multi-carbon products (a trend reproduced here, Figure 2a), and therefore in this study we believe that observed shifts in selectivity from CO to C₂H₄ is an indication of an increase in the local cation concentration at the cathode.

In comparison, in the catholyte-flow cell (and in the H-cell) the liquid electrolyte directly contacts the catalytic interface. Due to the absence of a diffusion gradient or an ion-selective membrane influencing cation transport to the cathode, the local concentration of cations is predominantly determined by the electrostatic forces arising from electrode polarization. Since the bulk electrolyte presents an abundant supply of cations, and the ions can migrate (unimpeded by an AEM) to the cathode where they accumulate at the outer Helmholtz plane, the local cation concentration is likely less sensitive to the bulk concentration.³⁸ We believe this to be a key reason for the relative insensitivity of product selectivity to the variation of electrolyte concentration (Figure 2b) in comparison to the results of the zero-gap cell.

Addition of Nafion to Cu catalysts is a common approach for altering the stability and selectivity of Cu GDEs. Selectivity trends, in Figure 1, with and without the addition of Nafion showed substantial differences. The selectivity towards CO was increased with a concurrent decrease in C₂H₄ selectivities on the addition of Nafion. These changes in product distribution and the previous reports/results of cation concentration dependent selectivity trends suggested to us that addition of Nafion could also be impacting the local cation concentration and therefore the selectivity.

We thus aimed to evaluate the local concentration of electrolyte cations at the catalyst to test the above hypothesis. Here, to gain some insight about the relative differences in cation distribution

across the catalyst-GDE interface following CO₂ electrolyzer operation, we conducted cross-section imaging with elemental mapping (FIB SEM EDS) for electrodes with and without Nafion.

The incorporation of Nafion into catalyst ink makes the catalyst layer more hydrophobic, as evidenced from the contact layer measurements (see SI Note S1). Incorporation of Nafion is also known to impart local hydrophobicity which restricts transport of water and solvated species. Nafion also increases local pH by trapping the OH⁻ in the vicinity of the electrode by Donan exclusion^{12,18,20,38} and an increase in local pH typically is known to result in an increase in the selectivity towards C₂₊ products.¹⁸ Our SEM-EDS images indicated a lower local cation concentrations around Cu nanoparticles (SEM-EDS in Figure 5) with Nafion than without. This could be a possible explanation for the switch in selectivity from C₂H₄ towards CO selectivity (selectivity shifts towards C₁-products) on the addition of Nafion.

Figure 5 SEM-EDS on cross sections of FIB-Milled post electrochemistry samples, a) Zero-Gap – 13% Nafion, b) Zero-Gap – 0% Nafion, and c) Catholyte-flow GDE -0% Nafion. [following experiments of 1 h at 100 mA/cm² in 1 M KOH]

We note that recent studies have shown cation movement in CO₂ electrolyzers to be dynamic and reversible¹⁵ and is therefore ideally assessed via in situ techniques³⁹. Such techniques are, however, not widely accessible, and furthermore have limited spatial resolution and ability to obtain quantitative information. Nonetheless, such methods could provide additional valuable insight and will be explored in future studies.

Examining the catalyst speciation

To evaluate the possible influence of catalyst surface speciation on the selectivity trends due to differing interfacial microenvironments, we carried out XPS and *operando* XAS measurements. More information about the XPS methods is available in the SI Note 2. In Figure 6 it is observed

that for the zero-gap and the H-cell conditions the Cu speciation was found to predominantly be metallic with traces of oxides whereas the catholyte-flow samples were observed to be at higher copper oxidation states. These surface speciation differences could be brought about by local pH differences. Singh et al., in their study on electrolyte effects pointed out the crucial role that the cations play in buffering the local pH by hydrolysis,⁴⁰ suggesting that as the solvated cations undergo hydrolysis, they release protons which results in lowering of the local pH. The local pH influences the thermodynamically stable phase of Cu, which may be a contributing factor to the speciation differences we observe here. For electrodes without Nafion tested in the zero-gap and the H-cell, a higher cation concentration around the catalyst is expected by virtue of the electrolyzers configuration which would result in lower local pH and a higher fraction of metallic surface speciation. Conversely, for the catholyte-flow configuration the presence of the flowing catholyte lowers the propensity of GDL flooding and subsequently lowers the local cation concentration. This lowered cation concentration and minimized buffering action on hydrolysis could result in a higher local pH and an oxide rich surface. It is essential to point out that the XPS spectra were acquired post-electrochemical testing. While external oxygen contamination was prevented using vacuum bags and/or conducting experiments in a glovebox with an inert transfer line (which is proven effective by the fact that we observe nearly fully reduced Cu^0 in some cases, e.g. Figure 6a), the possibility that some surface oxidation occurs upon removing the electrochemical bias while in contact with electrolyte cannot be ruled out. Additional XPS spectra were collected to investigate the impact of Nafion and electrolyte concentration on the Cu surface speciation. The analyzed data is shown in Figure S3 where it is observed that incorporation of Nafion in the catalyst layer for the zero-gap electrolyser leads to an increase in the Cu^{n+} speciation

(Figure S3b) while the electrolyte concentration on its own does not a substantial effect on the Cu surface speciation.

Figure 6 Cu LMM Auger spectra acquired by glovebox assisted XPS for samples without Nafion and tested in a) H-cell and b) catholyte-flow cell at -1.6V vs Ag/AgCl, and c) catholyte-flow cell and d) zero-gap cell at 100mAcm².

While XPS is a very surface-sensitive technique, it is not possible to perform these measurements on operating GDE cells. To gain more insight into Cu speciation under operating conditions, operando X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) was carried out. Both XANES and EXAFS spectra were acquired for the Cu K-edge using the catholyte-flow GDE and the zero-gap GDE cells at different electrolyte and Nafion concentrations. The results indicate that copper reduces from its

oxidized state seen under open circuit condition to Cu^0 under all operational conditions. This is in line with studies which also indicate that Cu is in its metallic state under applied bias.^{41,42} A drawback here is the bulk sensitive nature of the method, since the incident beam and the resulting fluorescence are both high-energy X-rays with a mean free path significantly longer than the average catalyst particle size. This implies that any signal from surface oxides would be very small compared to contribution from bulk Cu, so an absence of surface oxide based on the results of the XAS analysis cannot be entirely ruled out.

Figure 7 Effect of electrolyte concentration and Nafion on the surface speciation of the electrodes in the zero-gap (a) and (c), and catholyte-flow GDE (b) and (d) configurations. Cu K-edge XANES (a) and (b) and EXAFS (c) and (d) are shown for both the cell configurations. Reference spectra are shown in (a).

4. Conclusions

In this study we highlight the crucial role that the electrolyte concentration and ionomer (Nafion) content plays on selectivity trends. An important observation was the differing impact of these two parameters on selectivity trends for the three types of cell configurations investigated. The zero-gap configuration showed selectivity dependence on both the electrolyte concentration and Nafion content. At constant applied currents, the catholyte-flow GDE cell's selectivity was invariant with changing electrolyte concentrations but was observed to change with increasing ionomer content while the H-cell selectivity remained invariant on changing electrolyte concentrations and Nafion contents. We hypothesize that for the catholyte-flow GDE case, the flowing catholyte layer results in lesser propensity for the water to flood through the GDL, leading to a steady cation concentration dependent on the surface charge. Additionally, an increase in ionomer content could increase the local hydrophobicity and pH besides preventing infiltration of cations/solvated cations, thereby resulting in predominantly CO formation on electrodes with high ionomer content. As the H-cell was operated under fully flooded conditions, both the Nafion and the electrolyte didn't have an observable impact on the selectivity trends. The zero-gap cell conversely was seen to be affected by both the electrolyte concentration and Nafion content. The electrolyte concentration of the anolyte dictated the amount of crossed over cations while the Nafion content regulated the cations in the catalyst layer. In summary, it is reiterated that the performance of the electrolyzers is a composite of the catalyst and the catalytic microenvironment and that different cell configurations lead to differing catalytic microenvironments.

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Author Contributions

S.G. and G.A.E.N conceived the study and planned the experiments. S.G. drafted the manuscript, which was further revised by M.T.M, G.A.E.N. The electrochemistry experiments were carried out by S.G., G.A.E.N., and F.H while the electrode preparation was done by S.G., Z.Z., and C.M. The XPS measurements were performed by G.A.E.N., and D.S.B while the XPS data was analyzed, fitted, and plotted by S.G. All authors except D.S.B. contributed to the XAS beamtime experiments and the data analysis was done by G.A.E.N., and S.G. S.G., G.A.E.N., F.H., and M.T.M assisted with data analysis, regular discussions and commented on the manuscript.

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